

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part XI. Sorption of Methanol, Ethanol and Butanol Vapours by Casein and Casein fractions

UMA JOSHI, SURJIT K. DHILLON and BALWANT RAI PURI

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh

Manuscript received 28 January 1974; accepted 11 April 1975

Adsorption isotherms of methanol, ethanol and butanol on casein and its major fractions α - and β -caseins have been reported and analysed by B. E. T. as well as Harkins and Jura treatments. The values for specific surface area, as obtained from the above two techniques as well as from the knee of the isotherm of a given adsorbate, are in fair agreement but fall with increase in molecular dimensions of the adsorbate. The t -plots of the systems indicate that casein and its fractions contain micropores of width varying between 11.7 and 14.8 Å. The pores are too small to be easily accessible to butanol molecules. The differential free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes for different surface coverages by each adsorbate have been calculated. These quantities show an abrupt fall on the completion of the monolayer.

SEVERAL investigations on sorption of water vapour by a variety of proteins¹⁻³, including casein^{4,5} and its major fractions⁶ have been reported in recent years. Some workers^{7,8} are of the view that water is adsorbed on specific hydrophilic sites, although the exact role of chemical groups constituting such sites has not been understood. The perusal of the literature shows that similar studies on sorption of organic polar vapours have not received adequate attention although Benson⁹ et al have reported a comparative study on the sorption of water, methanol, ethanol, diethyl ether and ethyl chloride on egg albumin and the extent of sorption has been shown to vary with the ability of the adsorbate to form hydrogen bonds with the protein adsorbent. The present paper relates to the sorption of methanol, ethanol and butanol vapours by casein and its major fractions, α - and β -caseins, with a view to characterise these materials and to get a comparative set of values for free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes involved in the sorption of these vapours.

Experimental

Casein was isolated from bovine milk by Dunn's method¹⁰ and fractionated into α - and β -caseins as described before¹¹. Methanol and butanol (A.R.B. D.H.) were redistilled over sodium, while ethanol was recovered from rectified spirit by the usual distillations over lime and sodium. Adsorption isotherms were determined at 30° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by using McBain's balance with a quartz fibre spring having sensitivity 19.5 cm/g. It took nearly 2 hr for the attainment of equilibrium at each relative vapour pressure.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption isotherms of methanol, ethanol and butanol on unfractionated casein as well as α - and β -fractions, in terms of amounts adsorbed (g/100 g) at increasing relative pressures (r. v. ps), are plotted in

Fig 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The isotherms are of type II indicating formation of multilayers, as was reported in the case of water isotherms as well¹¹. Each curve shows a knee, which is more sharp in the case of methanol than that in the case of either ethanol or butanol, at ~ 0.2 r. v. p. Each isotherm can be split into three parts. The first part is convex to the pressure axis and ends at ~ 0.2 r. v. p., corresponding to the knee referred to above. This is followed by the second part which is almost linear and extends upto ~ 0.6 r. v. p. The amount of sorption for a given rise in r. v. p. is relatively small in this region. The isotherm in the third part swings almost vertically upward indicating a rapid rise in vapour sorption which may be due to unfolding of the molecules and exposure of fresh surfaces, the steps which ultimately lead to denaturation and degradation of casein itself.

The extent of adsorption on a given material decreases in the order.

i.e., it decreases with increase in the molecular dimensions of the adsorbate. This suggests parallel orientation of the adsorbate molecules on the surface.

The unfractionated casein is seen to take up more of methanol as well as ethanol vapour than either α -fraction or β -fraction. This anomaly which was observed in the case of sorption of water as well¹¹ may be due to mutual packing of the two fractions in inter- and intra-molecular spaces of one another, yielding larger effective surface area as well as more of 'active centres' constituted by edges and discontinuities in the unfractionated material. The α -fraction, however, takes up more of butanol than either the unfractionated product or β -fraction does. This, in a way, confirms the above view since some of the spaces, referred to above, may actually become too small, in the case of unfractionated casein, to be accessible to relatively larger molecules of butanol.

β -fraction is seen to be least active in sorbing any of the adsorbates at any of the relative vapour pressures examined in this work.

The isotherms were analysed by the application of B. E. T. equation. The plots for the whole casein are shown in Fig. 4, and are seen to be linear up to 0.35 r. v. p. for the sorption of all the three adsorbates, as required. The plots for the α - and β -fractions were also similar and are not given for reasons of space. The values of the constants C and V_m are given in Table 1. The net heats of sorption in the monolayer, $E_1 - E_L$, as calculated from the respective C values, included in Table 1, are seen to fall with increase in the length of the hydrocarbon chain of the adsorbate molecule. This indicates decrease in the intensity of interaction with increase in the hydrophobic character of the adsorbate. The specific surface areas, as calculated from V_m values, taking molecular areas of methanol, ethanol and butanol as 16.7, 25.1 and 52.3A², are given in Table 2.

The data were also analysed in the light of Harkin and Jura (H. J.) equation. The H. J. plots of $\log \frac{P}{P_0}$ against $1/V^2$ for the unfractionated casein are shown in Fig. 5. The plots for the α - and β -fractions were similar and are not given for reasons of space. The values for specific surface area (S) as obtained from the slopes (A) of the linear plots were obtained from the relationship

$$S = KA^{1/2}$$

where K is a constant, the value of which for alcohols is taken as 3.69 (12). These results are also included in Table 2.

Assuming that the knee in each isotherm represents completion of a monolayer, it was possible to obtain specific surface areas of all the three adsorbents from their respective isotherms (Fig. 1 and 2). These values are also included in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Methanol adsorption isotherms on bovine caseins at 30°.

TABLE 1— V_m , C AND ($E_1 - E_L$) AS DETERMINED FROM B. E. T. EQUATION FOR WATER, METHANOL, ETHANOL AND BUTANOL VAPOUR SORPTION.

Description of Sample	Methanol (water)			Ethanol			Butanol		
	V_m (g/100 g)	C	$E_1 - E_L$ cal/mole	V_m (g/100 g)	C	$E_2 - E_L$ cal/mole	V_m (g/100 g)	C	$E_1 - E_L$ cal/mole
Whole casein	6.2 (5.74)	19.02 (29.3)	1784 (2046)	5.72	9.90	1389	3.59	5.7	1056
α -casein	5.80 (5.48)	16.2 (23.01)	1687 (1900)	5.36	9.20	1345	3.85	6.7	1152
β -casein	4.83 (4.80)	15.99 (20.5)	1679 (1830)	4.37	8.72	1314	3.04	5.66	1048

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC SURFACE AREAS (M²/g) OBTAINED FROM B. E. T. EQUATION, H. J. PLOTS AND KNEE BEND OF THE ISOTHERM

Description of Sample	Methanol (water)			Ethanol			Butanol		
	B. E. T.	H. J.	knee bend	B. E. T.	H. J.	knee bend	B. E. T.	H. J.	knee bend
Whole casein	191 (202)	188 (201)	195 (200)	188	184	179	151	152	—
α -casein	181 (192)	174 (190)	184 (186)	176	171	168	162	165	—
β -casein	151 (168)	147 (164)	151 (161)	145	142	135	128	127	—

Fig. 2. Ethanol adsorption isotherms on bovine caseins at 30°C.

The corresponding values for specific surface areas, as obtained by analysing water isotherms, reported earlier¹¹, in a similar manner are also included in parentheses under the values calculated from methanol isotherms for the sake of comparison. It is seen that the values for a given material, as obtained by all the three methods, using a given adsorbate are fairly close to one another. This indicates applicability of all the three techniques for calculating specific surface area of casein and its fractions from a given adsorption isotherm. However, the value for any specific material is seen to vary with the nature of the adsorbate, generally decreasing with increase in molecular dimensions of the adsorbate. It appears highly probable that casein is not completely non-porous. It has probably micro-porous structure so that some of the very fine pores are not easily accessible to larger adsorbate molecules. This view was checked by plotting t-curves, as suggested by De-Boer¹³ et al in the case of adsorption of nitrogen on solids like carbons, silica gel etc. and as used by Hagymassy¹⁴ et al in the case of adsorption of water vapour on various biological systems. According to this method, the volume *V* of a vapour or gas adsorbed is plotted against a certain standard statistical thickness 't' of the adsorbed layer which had been obtained experimentally in the case of certain flat non porous adsorbents. A straight line should be obtained if the adsorbent under examination is non-porous. The presence of pores, however, causes a change in curvature of the line at a 't' value which corresponds to the dimensions of the pores present in the adsorbent. The value at that point becomes higher due to capillary condensation and slightly lower a little later, when pores are filled, due to

the reduction in effective surface area. This method is applicable to those adsorbate - adsorbent systems in which the number of stastical layers formed is less than 10. This condition is met with in the systems included in the present paper.

Fig. 3. Butanol adsorption isotherms on bovine caseins at 30°C.

Fig. 4. B. E. T. Plots of methanol, ethanol and butanol adsorption isotherms on bovine whole casein.

Fig. 5. H. J. plots of methanol, ethanol and butanol adsorption isotherms on bovine whole casein.

The isotherms on unfractionated casein shown in Fig 1 to 3, were converted into V-t plots (Fig 6) taking 't' values from the universal curve of Hagymassy¹⁴ et al. It is seen that in each case a sharp change in the direction of the V-t line is observed at a certain 't' value which indicates the presence of pores of a certain characteristic width. An additional sharp change in direction is observed at a subsequent value of 't'. The first break indicates higher sorption due to commencement of filling of pores while the second break indicates lower sorption due to filling up of the pores and consequent reduction of effective surface. The point at which the curve shows a change of curvature gives the number of adsorbed layers that can be formed in the pores and hence fixes the size of the pores. The average width of the pores, therefore, may be taken as lying between the thickness of the layer formed between the first and the second break. The values so obtained for casein and its major fractions from their respective t-plots of methanol and ethanol vapours taking molecular thickness as 4.01 and 4.58 Å respectively, are given in Table 3. It is significant to note that both the values for a given product are very close to one another, irrespective of differences in molecular dimensions of the adsorbates. This shows the reliability of this technique used for such calculations.

The t-plots for the sorption of butanol (Fig. 6), however, are linear and no break can be located. Casein, therefore, appears to behave as a non-porous material with regard to sorption of butanol. The reason, evidently, lies in the larger molecular diameter of butanol which on account of steric effects cannot become easily accessible to pores of very small dimensions.

Fig. 6. V-t plots of methanol, ethanol and butanol adsorption on bovine whole casein.

It is also significant to note (Table 3) that pore widths in α - and β -fractions are slightly larger than those in unfractionated casein. This supports the view expressed earlier that α - and β -fractions lie closely packed in unfractionated casein so that the latter has relatively more compact structure.

TABLE 3—PORE WIDTHS AS DETERMINED FROM V-t PLOTS OF METHANOL AND ETHANOL ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS

Description of sample	Methanol	Ethanol
	\bar{A}	\bar{A}
Whole casein	11.7—13.1	11.7—13.1
α -casein	12.5—14.7	11.9—14.5
β -casein	12.8—14.8	12.1—14.6

It was thought of interest to calculate thermodynamic functions such as free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes accompanying the transference of methanol, ethanol and butanol molecules from vapour state to the surface of casein. The differential values were obtained by using the equations (i), (ii) and (iii), respectively.

$$\Delta \bar{F} = RT(\ln x - d \ln x) \quad (i)$$

where x is the relative vapour pressure,

$$\Delta \bar{H} = \frac{R T_1 T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \ln \frac{x_2}{x_1} \quad (ii)$$

The isotherms determined at 30° and 40° were used for these calculations.

$$\bar{S}_s = S_G - \frac{\Delta \bar{H}}{T} \quad (iii)$$

The values of S_G for methanol and ethanol were obtained from standard tables. The corresponding values for butanol could not be obtained.

Fig. 7. Plots of differential free energy, differential heat and differential entropy respectively versus surface coverage (V/V_m) for bovine whole casein.

The differential free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes are plotted in Fig. 7. It is seen in the first instance that free energy change as well as enthalpy change for a given surface coverage decreases with increase in the length of the hydrocarbon chain in the molecule. This shows that hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions (between hydrophobic parts of casein and hydrophobic parts of alcohol molecules) are much weaker than hydrophilic-hydrophilic interactions in such systems.

The value of differential entropy change for ethanol, however, is higher than that of methanol at a given surface coverage. This is, obviously, due to greater standard entropy, S_G , of ethanol than that of methanol.

It is interesting to note that each value decreases with the extent of surface coverage, as expected, but it is highly significant that there is an abrupt change on the completion of a monolayer in every case. This offers strong support to the correctness of the monolayer capacity as obtained from B. E. T. and H. J. treatments as well as from the knee of the isotherms.

References

1. H. B. BULL and K. BREESE., *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1968, **128**, 488.
2. D. D. ELEY and R. B. LESLIE., *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 1002.
3. J. M. SEEHOF, B. KEILIN and S. W. BENSON., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2427.
4. R. W. GREEN., *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, (New Zealand), 1949, **77**, 313.
5. F. F. MELLON, A. H. KORN and S. R. HOOVER., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 827.
6. E. BERLIN, B. A. ANDERSON and M. J. PALLANSCH., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 303.
7. A. D. MCLAREN and J. W. ROWEN., *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1951, **7**, 289.
8. H. B. BULL., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1499.
9. S. W. BENSON and R. L. RICHARDSON., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2585.
10. M. S. DUNN., *Biochem. Preparations*, 1949, **1**, 22.
11. B. R. PURI and U. JOSHI., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
12. B. R. PURI and R. C. MALIK., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 763.
13. J. H. DEBOER, B. G. LINSEN, Th van der Plas and G. J. ZONDERVAN., *Catalysis*, 1965, **4**, 649.
14. J. HAGYMASSY, S. BRUNAUER and R. S. MIKHAIL., *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1969, **29**, 485.